

A STUDY ON UNICYCLIC GRAPH

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Abstract:

The harmonic index of a graph G is defined as the sum of the weight. In this paper we present the minimum harmonic indices for unicyclic graphs.

Key Words: Harmonic Index, Diameter & Unicyclic Graph

Introduction:

Let $G = (V, E)$ be a simple connected graph with vertex set $V(G)$ and edge set $E(G)$. The degree of a vertex v of G is denoted by $d(v)$. If $u, v \in V(G)$, then the distance between u and v is the length of a shortest $u - v$ path in G . The eccentricity of a vertex v is the greatest distance from v to any other vertex of G . The diameter of a graph is the maximum over eccentricities of all vertices of the graph and it is denoted by $D(G)$. For a graph G , the harmonic index $H(G)$ is defined as $H(G) = \sum_{u,v \in V(G)} \frac{2}{d(u)+d(v)}$ we know, this index first appeared in [4]. Zhong found the minimum and maximum values of the harmonic index for simple connected graphs, trees and unicyclic graphs and characterized the corresponding external graphs [8][9]. Wu et al. gave a best possible lower bound for the harmonic index of a triangle-free graph with minimum degree at least two and characterized the extremal graphs [7]. Den et al. considered the relation connecting the harmonic index $H(G)$ and the chromatic number $\chi(G)$ and proved that $\chi(G) \leq 2 H(G)$ by using the effect of removal of a minimum degree vertex on the harmonic index [3]. Mehdi Sabzevariet al. gave the exact formula for Merrifield Simmons and Hosoya indices of some special graphs namely ladder graph, prism graph and book graph [6]. Zohreh Bagheriaet al. computed the edge-Szeged and vertex-PI indices of some important classes of benzenoid systems [10]. Liuproved that $H(T) - D(T) \geq 5/6 - n/2$ and $(H(T))/(D(T)) \geq 1/2 + 1/(3(n-1))$ for n -vertex tree T with equality for path and proposed it as a conjecture for any connected graph of order n [5]. The first part of the above conjecture was proved in [1] for unicyclic graphs. In this work, we prove the second part of the conjecture viz. $(H(G))/(D(G)) \geq 1/2 + 4/(3(n-4))$ for $n \geq 7$, when G is unicyclic graph. We conclude this section with some notations and terminology. Let $G = (V, E)$ be a simple connected graph with vertex set $V(G)$ and edge set $E(G)$. If $d(v) = 1$, then v is said to be a pendant vertex of G . The edge incident with v is referred to as pendant edge and the vertex adjacent to v is referred as the support vertex of v . The set of neighbors of v is denoted by $N(v)$. A diametrical path of a graph is a shortest path whose length this equal to the diameter of the graph. As usual, C_n and P_n denote the path on n vertices, respectively. In a cycle C_n , two vertices, say u and v are said to be Diametrically opposite, if $d(u, v) = n/2$ when n is even and $d(u, v) = (n-1)/2$ when n is odd. Let $(U_n)^{(x,y)}$ be a unicyclic graph obtained from a cycle C_l by attaching two paths P_x and P_y to two diametrically opposite vertices of C_l such that $n = l+x+y$ For other notations in graph theory, maybe consulted [2].

Basic Results:

Lemma 1:

The function $f(x) = 1/(u+x) - 1/(u+x-1)$ is an increasing function on x for $x \geq 1$ and $u \geq 0$.

Lemma 2:

Let v be a pendent vertex of a connected graph G . then $H(G) > H(G-v)$.

Proof:

Let u be the support vertex of v . Then

$$\begin{aligned} H(G) - H(G-v) &= 2/(d(u)+1) + 2 \sum_{w \in N(u)-\{v\}} (1/(d(u)+d(w)) - 1/(d(u)+d(w)-1)) \\ &\geq 2/(d(u)+1) + 2 (d(u)-1) \sum 1/(d(u)+1) - 1/d(u) \text{ by lemma 1} \\ &= 2/(d(u)(d(u)+1)) \\ &> 0 \end{aligned}$$

Hence $H(G) > H(G-v)$.

Analyzing the unicyclic graphs and its diametrical path, we have the following observation.

Observation:

If $G \cong C_n$ is a unicyclic graph on n vertices, then at least one of the end vertices of the diametrical path of G must be a pendant vertex.

Main Result:

In this section, we give the sharp lower bound of the relationship involving the harmonic index and diameter of connected unicyclic graphs.

Theorem 1:

Let G be a unicyclic graph of order $n \geq 7$ and diameter $D(G)$. Then $(H(G))/(D(G)) \geq 1/2 + 4/(3(n-4))$, where

equality holds if and only if $G \cong (U_{(n,4)})^{(1,n-5)}$.

Proof:

Case 1: Let $G \cong C_n$ then $H(G) = n/2$, if n is even, then $D(G) = n/2$.

Hence $(H(G))/(D(G)) = 1 \geq 1/2 + 4/(3(n-4))$. If n is odd, then $D(G) = (n-1)/2$. Hence

$$(H(G))/(D(G)) = 1 + 1/(n-1) \geq 1/2 + 4/(3(n-4))$$

Case 2: Let $G \neq C_n$. Then G has at least one pendant vertex. Also by the observation, at least one of the end vertices of the diametrical path of G is a pendant vertex. Let P be a diametrical path of G . Now continue to remove pendant vertices from G so that P remains its diametrical path. Let the resulting graph be G' and v_1, v_2, \dots, v_k be the vertices in the order they were deleted. Then we have,

$$H(G) > H(G-v_1) > \dots > H(G - \sum_{i=1}^k v_i) = H(G')$$

By Lemma 2 and

$$D(G) = D(G-v_1) = \dots = D(G - \sum_{i=1}^k v_i) = D(G')$$

Clearly G' is also a unicyclic graph consisting of a cycle of length l together with at most two pendant paths, say P_x and P_y incident with two vertices of C_l , say u and v , such that $n = k+l+x+y$.

Sub Case 2.1: Let $x = 0$ and $y = 1$. In this case, $G' \cong (U_{(n-k, n-k-1)})^{0,1}$

$H(G') = (n-k)/2 - 1/5$. If l is even, then $D(G') = (n-k+1)/2$. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} (H(G'))/(D(G')) &= (5n-5k-2)/(5(n-k+1)) \\ &= 1 - 7/(5(n-k+1)) \\ &\geq 1/2 + 4/(3(n-4)) \quad \text{since } n-k \geq 5. \end{aligned}$$

If l is odd, then $D(G') = (n-k)/2$. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} (H(G'))/(D(G')) &= (5n-5k-2)/(5(n-k)) \\ &= 1 - 2/(5(n-k)) \\ &\geq 1/2 + 4/(3(n-4)) \quad \text{since } n-k \geq 4. \end{aligned}$$

Sub Case 2.2: Let $x = 0$ and $y \geq 2$. In this case, $H(G') = (n-k)/2 - 2/15$. If l is even, then

$D(G') = (n-k+y)/2$. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} (H(G'))/(D(G')) &= (15n-15k-4)/(15(n-k+y)) \\ &= 1 - (15y+4)/(15(n-k+y)) \\ &= 1/2 + (15l+8)/(30(2(n-k)-l)) \\ &\geq 1/2 + 4/(3(n-4)) \quad \text{since } n-k = l+y \text{ and } l \geq 4. \end{aligned}$$

If l is odd, then $D(G') = (n-k+y-1)/2$. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} (H(G'))/(D(G')) &= (15n-15k-4)/(15(n-k+y-1)) \\ &= 1 - (15y-11)/(15(n-k+y-1)) \\ &= 1/2 + (15l+7)/(30(2(n-k)-l-1)) \\ &\geq 1/2 + 4/(3(n-4)) \quad \text{since } n-k = l+y \text{ and } l \geq 3 \end{aligned}$$

Sub Case 2.3: Let $x = 1, y = 1$. If u and v are nonadjacent, then $G' \cong (U_{(n-k, 1)})^{1,1}$

Clearly $H(G') = (n-k)/2 - 2/5$. If l is even, then $D(G') = (n-k)/2 + 1$. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} (H(G'))/(D(G')) &= (5n-5k-4)/(5(n-k+2)) \\ &= 1 - 14/(5(n-k+2)) \\ &= 1 - 14/(5(l+4)) \quad \text{since } n-k = l+2 \\ &\geq 1/2 + 4/(3(n-4)). \end{aligned}$$

If l is odd, then $D(G') = (n-k+1)/2$. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} (H(G'))/(D(G')) &= (5n-5k-4)/(5(n-k+1)) \\ &= 1 - 9/(5(n-k+1)) \\ &= 1 - 9/(5(l+3)) \quad \text{since } n-k = l+2 \\ &\geq 1/2 + 4/(3(n-4)). \end{aligned}$$

Sub Case 2.4: Let $x = 1$ and $y \geq 2$. If u and v are adjacent.

Clearly $H(G') = (n-k)/2 - 3/10$ and $D(G') = y + 2$. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} (H(G'))/(D(G')) &= (5n-5k-3)/(10(y+2)) \\ &\geq (5n-5k-3)/(10(n-2)) \\ &= 1 - (5n+5k-17)/(10(n-2)) \\ &\geq 1/2 + 4/(3(n-4)). \end{aligned}$$

If u and v are nonadjacent, then $G' \cong (U_{(n-k,1)})^{(1,y)}$. Clearly $H(G') = (n-k)/2 + 1/3$. If l is even, then $D(G') = (n-k+y+1)/2$. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} (H(G'))/(D(G')) &= (3n-3k-2)/(3(n-k+y+1)) \\ &= 1 - (3y+5)/(3(n-k+y+1)) \\ &\geq 1/2 + 4/(3(n-4)). \end{aligned}$$

If l is odd, then $D(G') = (n-k+y)/2$. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} (H(G'))/(D(G')) &= (3n-3k-2)/(3(n-k+y)) \\ &= 1 - (3y+2)/(3(n-k+y)) \\ &\geq 1/2 + 4/(3(n-4)). \end{aligned}$$

Sub Case 2.5: Let $x \geq 2$ and $y \geq 2$. If u and v are adjacent, then $H(G') = (n-k)/2 + 7/30$ and $D(G') = x + y + 1 = n - k - 1 + 1$. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} (H(G'))/(D(G')) &= (15n-15k-7)/(30(n-k-1+1)) \\ &\geq 1/2 + 4/(3(n-4)) \end{aligned}$$

If u and v are nonadjacent, then $H(G') = H((U_{(n-k,l)}^{(X,y)}) = (n-k)/2 + 4/15$ and $D(G') \leq D((U_{(n-k,l)}^{(X,y)})$. If l is even $D(G') \leq (n-k+x+y)/2$. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} (H(G'))/(D(G')) &= (15n-15k-8)/(15(n-k+x+y)) \\ &= (15n-15k-8)/(15(2(n-k)-1)) \\ &= 1/2 + (15l-16)/(30(2(n-k)-1)) \\ &\geq 1/2 + 4/(3(n-4)) . \end{aligned}$$

If l is odd. $D(G') \leq (n-k+x+y-1)/2$. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} (H(G'))/(D(G')) &> (15n-15k-8)/(15(n-k+x+y-1)) \\ &= (15n-15k-8)/(15(2(n-k)-1-1)) \\ &= 1/2 + (15l-1)/(30(2(n-k)-1-1)) \\ &\geq 1/2 + 4/(3(n-4)) . \end{aligned}$$

For proving the equality, assume that $(H(G))/(D(G)) = 1/2 + 4/(3(n-4))$. Since $D(G) \leq n-2$, $(H(G))/(n-2) \leq (H(G))/(D(G))$ for all t .

So our search is to find that t , for which $D(G) = n-2$ and $(H(G))/(D(G)) = 1/2 + 4/(3(n-4))$. $(U_{(n,3)}^{(0,n-3)})$, $(U_{(n,3)}^{(1,n-4)})$, $(U_{(n,3)}^{(2,n-5)})$,

$(U_{(n,4)}^{(0,n-4)})$, $(U_{(n,4)}^{(1,n-5)})$ and $(U_{(n,4)}^{(2,n-6)})$ are the unicyclic graphs with $D(t) = n-2$. But $(U_{(n,4)}^{(1,n-5)})$ is the only graph that satisfies the equality. Hence $G \sim (U_{(n,4)}^{(1,n-5)})$ and it is easy to check $(H((U_{(n,4)}^{(1,n-5)}))/(D((U_{(n,4)}^{(1,n-5)}))) = 1/2 + 4/(3(n-4))$

Remark 3.1. If $n \leq 6$, this lower bound is not true. One such graph,

$$(H(G))/(D(G)) = 13/20 \leq 2/3 = 1/2 + 4/(3(n-4)).$$

This result seems true for any connected graph of order n , that is not a tree, and we propose it as a conjecture as follows.

Conjecture 1. Let G be a simple connected graph, that is not a tree, of order

$n \geq 7$ and diameter $D(G)$. Then $H(G) - D(G) \geq 5/2 - n/2$ and $(H(G))/(D(G)) \geq 1/2 + 4/(3(n-4))$,

Where equality holds if and only if $t \sim (U_{(n,4)}^{(1,n-5)})$.

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